

Bank Permata Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Permata Syariah and Conventional Banks using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Permata Syariah and Conventional Banks based on journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Bank Permata Sharia Business Unit; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Permata Syariah and Conventional Banks, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

As time goes by, the sharia-based economy is growing rapidly in Indonesia. One of the factors influencing sharia-based economic growth in Indonesia is the majority Muslim population and increasing knowledge about sharia in the economic sector. The characteristics of a sharia-based economy are the existence of rules that have the advantage of being an economic system with religious legal guarantees based on the outline of halal and haram rules (Rusby, 2017). This certainly encourages financial institutions, such as banks that carry out activities to collect and manage funds from the public, to establish sharia-based banking. According to Constitution no. 10 of 1998, article 1 part number two explains that banks are institutions that collect funds from the public in the form of savings, then distribute them to the public in the form of credit or other forms. Banking was founded with the aim of improving people's living standards (Fahmi, 2014).

The aim of establishing Bank Permata Syariah is to carry out sharia-based economic activities in the banking industry. Bank Permata Syariah is a subsidiary of Bank Permata Conventional which was formed through the merger of five banks: PT Bank Bali Tbk., PT Bank Universal Tbk., PT Bank Prima Express, PT Bank Artha Media, and PT PAL Patriot. The result of the merger of these companies was the birth of the name Bank Permata, which is an

inseparable unit (Hanafi, 2017). On April 26 2006, Bank Permata achieved the top ranking in excellent service according to Bank Info Magazine. The Bank Permata logo was introduced on February 18 2003, which has the colors blue, red and green. These three colors have meanings, namely blue reflects justice, red reflects enthusiasm, and green reflects prosperity (Hanafi, 2017).

Several articles spread on the internet have not published much research on Bank Permata Syariah. According to the Garba Rujukan Digital (Garuda) website, the last research on Bank Permata Syariah was carried out in 2019. This shows that there has been no significant increase in research on Bank Permata Syariah. However, for research on Conventional Permata Banks, in 2022 there will be around 60 articles or documentation published. This shows that there is an increase in research on Conventional Permata Banks.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional uses library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Permata Syariah and Conventional Banks, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Permata Syariah and Conventional Banks, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Based on the book published by PT Bank Permata entitled " Sustainability Report 2020 Sustainability Report ", Bank Permata has many achievements in the sharia bank category. One of them is ranked first in best performance for sharia business units (Laporan Keberlanjutan 2020 sustainability report, 2020). In meeting customer needs, Bank Permata has a vision to grow and develop by fostering partnerships and creating meaningful value for stakeholders as well as a set of values called I-(PRICE). The abbreviation of I-(PRICE) is Integrity, Partnership, Responsiveness, Innovation, Caring, Excellence. These values are the brand promise to " make life worthwhile " in the implementation of behavior to run the company, work, colleagues, investors, customers and regulators (Permatabank, 2013).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can

be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The research object is Permata Syariah and Conventional Banks. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Permata originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Permata " for the entire year (20 08 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional

This section of the chapter examines the results of searches for scientific publications regarding Permata Syariah and Conventional Banks starting from 2008 to 2022. The results show that there are fluctuations or ups and downs every year, especially starting in 2017 which experienced an increase in publications compared to 2008 to 2016. In 2019, the highest number of publications was 8 articles. So, the average scientific publication regarding Bank Sinarmas Syariah and Conventional is more than 2 articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank Sinarmas Permata and Conventional by year period

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2008	1	2015	2	2020	5
2011	1	2016	2	2021	3
2012	2	2017	3	2022	4
2013	1	2018	2		
2014	2	2019	8		
Total 36					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Next are affiliates or institutions that publish research articles about Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional. The names of affiliates or institutions that research Bank Permata Syariah in the list of 36 data (RIS) only publish one journal. The following institutions and journals publish other complications regarding Islamic and conventional gem banks: AccoPurba, AP (2021). Analysis Of Financial Statements In Measuring Financial Performance at PT Permata Bank Tbk., Accounting and Business., Accrual., An-Nida: Islamic Communication Journal, BENING., Biormatics: Scientific journal of teaching and educational science faculties., Business., Economics and Entrepreneurship., Dynasty International Journal of Management Science., EDUKA: Journal of Education, Law and Business., E-Journal of Management., EKONOMIA., Equator Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship (EJME)., Fair Value: Scientific Journal of Accounting and Finance., Indonesian Journal of Economics and Management., Journal of Engineering, Technology, and Applied Science., JOURNAL of LEGAL RESEARCH., Journal of Tourism Destination and Attraction., JOURNAL OF OFFICE ADMINISTRATION., Muhammadiyah Accounting Journal (JAM)., Economic Journal., Journal of Economics and Industry., Journal of Effective Economics., EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research., Scientific Journal of COMPUTATION., Scientific Journal of Batanghari University Jambi., Journal of Justisia Ekonomika: Masters in Sharia Economic Law., Journal Management, Business and Entrepreneurship., Mirai Management Journal., Accounting Research Journal., Indonesian Journal of Marketing Science., Contingency: Management Scientific Journal., MANDAR: Management Development and Applied Research Journal., Perspective., PRIVATE LAW., SITEKIN: Journal of Science, Technology and Industry., Soso-Q: Management Journal., STRING (Technology Research and Innovation Writing Unit).

The following table shows the names of researchers who published within the scope of Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional. The majority of researchers in the table have only published once, but Hieronimus Erwin Indrawan has published twice.

Table 2. Researcher productivity regarding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional

Researcher	Number of Publications
Hieronimus Erwin Indrawan	2
Riki Arswendi, Dewi Sad Tanti, Andi Herlina, Ary Natalina, C. Widi Pratiwi, Andi Nariya, Wati Aris Astuti, Noneng, Stanty Aulia Rachmat, Gendro Wiyono, Agus Dwi Cahya, Friska Airin Yusvita Arvianti, Agus Subardi, Marlyn Pricillia Laluyan, Arlina Pratiwi Purba, Kaman Nainggolan, Bryan Givan, Ismail Jamil, Silmi, Kevry Ramdany, Yudi Mufti Prawira, Iwan Iskandar, Stenly Jacobus Ferdinandus, Achmad Fatoni, Normalisa, Ahmad Fikri Zulfikar, Phong Thanh Nguyen, Hapzi Ali, Agung Hudaya, Dwi Haryono Wiratno, Jihan Fadlilah Zatayumni, Mahesa Dewa, Putri Dzakiyyah Sholihah, Rizki Aria Fahreza, Median Wiwisata, Wiwi Afriani, Theresia Meyda Ruliani Situmorang, Dhenny Asmarazisa, Nadia Reynilda Aulia Putri, Hasbi Assidiki Mauluddi, Dadang Hermawan, Irwan, Gunawan, Razak Munir, Yenni Rachmawati Setiawan, Merlina Nur Lestari, Fetty Nurmala Rossi, Yulidayanti, Arief Rachmawan Assegaf, Noryani, Ivan Pangemanan, Lisbeth Mananeke, Jacky SB Sumarauw, Ida Bagus Gede Witnyana, Ida Bagus Sudiksa, Purwanti, Tuti Handayani, Achmad Kurniawan, Warsidi, Ginting Gerinata, Murti Lestari, Lincoln Arsyad	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional

The results of searching for research articles regarding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) resulted in 36 articles. Then the article was exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, input and analyzed with VOSviewer, so that the following results were obtained:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional

1. First, financial performance after the merger.
2. Second, the health level uses financial ratios, RGEC, and during the Covid-19 pandemic.
3. Third, the influence of the Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR on capital.
4. Fourth, the influence of promotional costs and funding costs on Third Party Funds/DPK.
5. Fifth, analyze profitability ratios.
6. Sixth, the influence of interest costs, promotion costs and employee salary costs on net interest income.
7. Seventh, application of fair value to assess company assets.
8. Eighth, the influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, and Non-Performing Loans /NPL on Return On Assets /ROA.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Permata Bank Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 15 topics related to the performance of Bank Permata employees, namely:

1. Work culture.
2. Work discipline.
3. Leadership.
4. Compensation.
5. Interpersonal communication.
6. Performance quality.
7. Work environment.
8. Work motivation.
9. Career development.
10. Intensive giving.
11. Providing employee cooperative loans.
12. Recruitment.
13. Employee development.
14. Customer service representative performance assessment with AHP.
15. Selection.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Permata Bank Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 3 topics related to the behavior of Bank Permata customers, namely:

1. Service quality.
2. Product quality.
3. Promotion.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Permata Bank Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 5 Research topics relate to Bank Permata financing products, namely:

1. First, resolving defaults on bad credit card bills through debt collectors.
2. Second, the influence of the precautionary principle, the performance of the debtor's financial statements, and the Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR on credit provision.
3. Third, the influence of attitudes and subjective norms on customers' interest in choosing unsecured credit.
4. Fourth, providing credit with collateral rights.

5. Fifth, credit agreement without collateral according to standard clauses.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Permata Sharia Business Unit

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 4 research topics related to Bank Permata Sharia Business Unit, namely:

1. First, the promotional mix for sharia business units.
2. Second, the completion of the Mudharabah contract is problematic.
3. Third, the role, duties and authority of the notary.
4. Fourth, synergy with IZI.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Other Issues at Bank Permata

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 3 Research topics relate to issues at Bank Permata, namely:

1. First, information technology risk management to prevent hacking cases using the RiskIT Framework.
2. Second, the internet banking information system uses AMOS.
3. Third, the credit card registration application system.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Permata Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Bank Permata Sharia Business Unit; and (6) Other issues.

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